

Working with Family in Psychotherapy in the Process of Loss and Grief

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Abstract

Throughout our lives, we may experience situations that we can control as well as situations that we cannot control. The most severe of these situations that we cannot control is undoubtedly the process of loss and grief. The loss of a person with whom we had positive experiences in our lives, who had an important place in our lives, affects us deeply. Loss and the grieving process that follows is a normal period. The reactions experienced by individuals in this process are natural and it is not right to intervene. The person may go through periods of grief such as extreme sadness, constant crying and insomnia, depression, withdrawal from life, isolation from social environments, withdrawal from home, etc. The grieving process first begins with shock and denial. Then the individual experiences restlessness, inner distress, withdrawal, and social withdrawal. If he/she starts to adapt to life after overcoming these phases, he/she overcomes the grieving process as he/she should. However, if there is no decrease in these behaviors, if there is no adaptation to life and if there is no change in emotions, a psychological problem has occurred. After a loss in the family, the grieving process for children and parents may not occur at the same time. Children have a different grieving process than adults. They may engage in behaviors of denial or overreact to the loss. Children's acceptance of this loss and their usual reaction processes may vary according to their age. If individuals experience psychological problems such as depression, anxiety, panic attacks, increased alcohol use, unhappiness, hopelessness, anger, guilt, living in the past, and denial of death, even though a certain amount of time has passed within the family, this indicates that they cannot adapt to daily life. Individuals should seek professional help in this process. The

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involvement of the family in the psychotherapy process during the period of loss and grief gradually reduces their distress and they begin to live their lives independently.

Keywords: *Loss, Grief, Psychotherapy Process, Family*

1. Introduction

In general terms, death can be defined as the end of the life state of the living being and its qualitative change of form. In the case of living things, death means the complete loss of the vital functions of the cell, organ or organism or the cessation of the state of being alive (Tanha and İnci, 2009).

Death is the most painful concrete loss experienced by the individual because it is an end and irreversible. After such a loss, the individual may feel lonely and helpless in a certain meaninglessness and emptiness with complex emotions such as abandonment, guilt, and anger, which destroy the base of trust and attachment (Bildik, 2013).

Death is undoubtedly an inevitable process that every human being experiences. The grieving process that awaits individuals after the loss is difficult and painful. When evaluating the coping method used by the family in the grieving process, factors that may affect the grieving process and the family's grief reactions should be taken into consideration. These factors include the developmental stages of the family life cycle, family values and belief systems, the role of the bereaved individual in the family, ties with family members, the family's level of functionality, culture, traditions, taboos, the type of loss, the family's emotional response pattern (relief, avoidance, blame, fear, distortion, etc.) and support networks (Humphrey and Zimpfer 2008, Puri and Treasaden 2010, Jeffreys 2011, Kissane 2014).

The loss of a spouse brings with it the loss of many roles for the survivor. Individuals can often experience a sense of helplessness socially, emotionally, physically, and sexually. The challenging process of grief is usually the first year of loss. The bereaved spouse is faced with longing, increased responsibilities, children, and workload. In children, the situation is more complex.

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The child's understanding of death depends on many factors such as age, previous encounters with death, having a terminal illness, cultural and religious characteristics, and whether death is expected or sudden (Ekşi 2011).

The grieving process is usually experienced within the family and does not require intervention. However, if this process affects the person's life in a negative way, if it is at a level that prevents daily activities and if it continues to increase in severity despite a long time after the loss, there is a problem. In this case, it is inevitable to seek professional help for grieving family members.

2. The Concept of Death in Evolutionary Terms

The perspective on the phenomenon of death may differ depending on evolutionary periods. For example, children's understanding, digestion and acceptance of death is limited by their level of cognitive, social and emotional maturity. In this case, the perception of the phenomenon of death by the individual reveals the importance of the way, place and time of explaining the subject to the individual. As a family, it is useful to give the individual a healthy perspective on death.

Death is not a one-dimensional concept but has five major cognitive sub-concepts. These concepts can be listed as follows:

- **Dysfunctionality-Finality:** Death necessitates the cessation of all functions such as movement, emotion, thought
- **Inevitability:** Everyone will die sooner or later
- **Irreversibility:** The impossibility of returning to life
- **Causality:** Death always has physical or biological causes
- **Universality:** The fact that every living thing will face death without exception (Koytak, 2008, Yılmaz, 2012)

2.1. The Concept of Death in Childhood

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Children think of death as a phenomenon distant from themselves, their family and their immediate environment. Since the concept of death is abstract, young children may not be able to perceive the concept of death correctly. This is because this is the period we call the pre-processing period, in which children embrace everything concretely.

In addition, children are interested in the concept of death at a very early age. They try to understand death by listening to their elders and close relatives, hearing news about death in the media, seeing a dying person, animal, or plant. However, in our society, children are usually taught about death through religious teachings. Conversations such as "God has taken him/her with him/her", "He/she is now in heaven", "He/she is watching us from above" are abstract, complex, and incomprehensible for children.

The child expresses the phenomenon of death, what he/she experiences and feels, in his/her speeches, drawings and most of all in his/her games.

Since the concept of death has not developed in infancy between 0-3 years of age, the baby associates death with separation. Separation of the caregiver from the baby is a serious problem for the baby. Children between the ages of 2-6 are generally self-centered. For a child between the ages of 2 and 6, the idea that life will end in death has not yet been formed. During this period, the child grows up with the awareness that all living things will live. The feeling that the deceased person will be somewhere else and will return is dominant. However, the fact that the separation is long and the person who has left has not yet returned causes an increase in the level of anxiety in the child.

Children between 6 and 10 years of age do not show overt death anxiety and at this age they are most afraid of being injured or disabled. However, terminally ill children are aware that something bad and serious is happening to them. Among the concepts of death, dysfunctionality, inevitability, finality, and universality are perceived by children between the ages of 7 and 10, while irreversibility is fully perceived by adolescents. A young person between the ages of 12 and 18 in the abstract processing period has now learned that death is an irreversible process.

In order to help children in this period, it is very important to know their developmental stages well, to know the child well and to take the right actions at the right time.

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2.2. The Concept of Death in Adolescence

It is a fact that the phenomenon of death starts in childhood and continues in adolescence. However, unlike in childhood, there is an increase in the adolescent's interest and curiosity in the phenomenon of death. Adolescents' perception of life is at extremes due to their age. Therefore, their level of patience towards experiences that remind them of death is maximum.

The phenomenon of death is common in adolescence. Thoughts such as the moment of death and the aftermath arouse curiosity. However, adolescents fear aging rather than death in this period. The phenomenon of death becomes more abstract in adolescents. With the formation of abstract thoughts, adolescents develop the ability to think symbolically, analyze their own thoughts, and make metaphorical interpretations with the phenomenon of death, since imagining death requires worry, fear, and complex mental schemes. Thus, adolescents are able to make religious and philosophical interpretations by understanding the irreversibility of the concept of death.

2.3. The Concept of Death in Adulthood

In adulthood, the main problem is the individual's attempt to find satisfactory solutions to this situation by perceiving that death carries the concepts of dysfunctionality-finality, inevitability, irreversibility, causality, and universality.

With advancing age, death makes its presence felt more and more, and it can be said that many negative emotions experienced in adulthood are caused by the fear of death and the helplessness to be experienced afterwards. Reconsideration of life and adaptation to death are among the important changes seen towards the end of life.

The concept of death in adults is often a combination of cultural-social life, customs and traditions, emotional and personal issues, religious beliefs. For the adult, death is a biological event that can happen to anyone.

3. Loss and Grief

Death is a sad event caused by the loss of a loved one. It may not be easy for individuals to face death after losing a loved one. Individuals may be more affected after sudden and unexpected deaths and some traumatic problems may arise.

It is important to know how to cope with this situation following the loss that we will encounter at any time in our lives and how to help both ourselves and our relatives during the grieving process in order to overcome it in a healthy way.

Grief is a collection of reactions such as sadness, inner distress, regrets, longing, and sorrow after a loss. The grieving process is a process that must be experienced for the person to heal. How long it takes the individual to overcome this process varies. In a healthy grieving process, the individual:

- Accepts that death is a real phenomenon,
- Expresses the pain and sadness caused by death,
- Adapts to and lives in an environment where the deceased person is not present,
- Regulates their emotional connection with the deceased.

The loss of a member of the family can disrupt the balance of relationships. Relationships, roles and responsibilities within the family may need to be reorganized. Despite differences in personal characteristics, the family acts as a whole in the process of loss and grief.

The personality traits of the grieving family members, the degree of relationship with the deceased, religious values, beliefs, the cause of death of the deceased, socio-economic status, the level of perception of death, the support they receive from their family and close environment determine the quality of their reactions during the grieving process.

Due to the interpersonal differences observed in the grieving process and the diversity of factors affecting it, grief can be analyzed in three different ways.

- Healthy grief

- Pathological grief
- Traumatic grief

3.1. Healthy Grief

Healthy Grief is to be able to define the social, emotional, mental, physical and behavioral reactions that occur in individuals after death as a natural consequence of loss. It is possible for the individual to recover and return to the state of balance before the loss by completing the stages of the healthy grieving process.

In this type of grief, it is natural to have reactions as shown in the table.

Table 1. Common and Usual Grief Reactions of Individuals

Physical Reactions	Cognitive Reactions	Emotional Reactions	Behavioral Reactions
Stomach burning	Denial of death	State of shock	Searching for the deceased
Breathlessness	Sudden episodes	Sadness and grief	Absent-mindedness
Choking sensation	Thinking the deceased is alive	Excessive anger	Crying fits
Disturbance from loud noises	Conversing with the deceased	Blaming oneself and others	Avoidance of the deceased person's belongings, not wanting to see them
Feeling of fatigue	Seeing the deceased in dreams	Feeling of loneliness	Social withdrawal
Loss or increase in appetite		Loss of hope for life	Sleep problems

3.2. Pathological Grief

As a result of the loss of a valued and loved one, individuals go through a psychologically, physiologically and cognitively challenging period. In this difficult period,

grief, distress, hopelessness, longing, regret, mental confusion may cause physical reactions such as headaches, nausea, etc. and psychological reactions such as withdrawal, lack of speech, and lack of communication with others. As time passes, the symptoms of acute grief decrease in severity and the person returns to their daily routines. However, when the grief process does not reach a solution and even becomes over reactive, it is thought that the situation is no longer normal.

Pathological grief can be defined as a problem that manifests itself as a result of the gradual deterioration of the functionality of the person experiencing loss in personal, social and professional life areas, although at least six months have passed after the loss (Bildik, 2013).

In this type of grief, it is observed that the person cannot go through the normal stages and remains stuck in one stage. In this case, the individual's grief reactions continue to increase. Pathological grief is a set of thoughts that occupy the mind about the deceased person with denial of death, regrets, sorrow, sadness, longing, and anger. The person may experience permanent and persistent mourning, denial of death, trust problems, tantrums, difficulty in organizing and continuing his/her life, and a feeling of emotional emptiness. It is inevitable to talk about pathological grief when these symptoms last for at least 6 months and make it difficult for the person to function and adapt to life.

3.3. Traumatic Grief

People may face unexpected and sudden pain at some times in their lives. People's lives can change unexpectedly. The situations that create these situations are called traumatic events.

Trauma is divided into two main groups. The first group is traumatic situations caused by humans: War, sexual harassment, torture, accidents, etc. The second group is traumatic situations caused by natural events: Earthquake, flood, landslide etc.

Traumatic grief is a problem that occurs as a result of the gradual deterioration of the functionality of the person experiencing loss in emotional, social, cognitive, personal and professional life areas, although at least six months have passed after the loss. In the traumatic grieving process, the individual's reactions to the grief gradually increase and become longer in duration.

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Types of death such as death due to illness, sudden death, death by suicide, death by homicide; the existence of a dependent relationship between the deceased and the person left behind, feelings of guilt, depression or psychological discomfort, inability to adapt to losses increase the grieving process and its severity.

With the dual effect of trauma and loss, the process of resolution of the individual's grief reactions takes a long time. This situation causes stress. In traumatic grief, the individual feels separation anxiety deeply.

Since traumatic grief occurs within the family, which is the smallest unit of society, it is very important in traumatic grief interventions to reveal the resilience and strengths of the family through familial and social methods and to make decisions about what can be done instead of focusing on pathologies with individual methods.

Family resilience is the ability of the family to survive financially and emotionally despite these devastating life challenges, to act in unity, to regroup and regain strength, and to get through this period.

3.4. Complications of the Grieving Process

Grief is a normal situation that occurs after death and that every person experiences from time to time in their lives. It would be wrong to characterize every reaction in this process as unusual.

The mental, physical, emotional and social changes experienced in the first weeks or months after a death or loss are natural reactions in the grieving process.

The way each person experiences the grieving process varies according to the cause of death, the bond between the deceased person, personality traits or habits of coping with stressful situations. Emotions such as anger, sadness, constant crying, guilt, numbness, grief; cognitive difficulties such as difficulty in focusing, paying attention, reasoning power; physical symptoms such as weakness, sore body, lethargy, constant sleeping or inability to sleep, or detachment from the social environment, shutting oneself in the house or room, and the desire to stay away from people are among the reactions that can be seen during the grieving process.

4. Family in Loss and Grief

The family is a system in which individuals have mutual experiences. The family's communication with each other, values, socio-cultural characteristics are important for the development of the skills to overcome difficulties. Because of this, the process of loss and grief involves not just one person but the whole family. The death of a family member often leads to multiple losses such as hopelessness, pessimism, negative thoughts, inability to enjoy life. This situation allows the family to reconsider important factors such as energy, time and the correct management of the process. Despite individual differences, the family as a whole determines how grief will be experienced, because grief is a family problem. It has been observed that families manage the grieving process healthily through adaptive, dysfunctional, or intermediate techniques. Adaptive methods require strong communication between family members, financial and emotional support, mutual sharing of feelings and thoughts, and the ability to cope with conflict. Family members who use dysfunctional methods experience high rates of fighting, lack of communication, and lack of commitment. On the other hand, families using intermediate methods show factors such as difficulty in commitment, difficulties in communication, and low success rates. Factors affecting the grieving process can be listed as the cultural characteristics, values and beliefs of the family, the role of the deceased, the manner of death, age, the nature of the relationship with the deceased and the level of functionality of the family.

4.1. Parents in the Process of Loss and Grief

Parents' grieving process becomes more manageable with the right information and communication. The opposite results in increased negative emotions such as miscommunication, increased anxiety, and anger. The most crucial aspects of parents' behavior during the grieving process are loyalty, trust, empathy, and patience. After accepting the loss, parents digest the phenomenon of death over time. The most important source of support in this process is the positive and remedial communication of spouses with each other. In this process, it is important for parents not to experience the loss alone, to take care of their physical needs, to talk about the deceased person when they are ready, to cope with memories of the person lost, to talk to people who have experienced similar losses, to visit the grave of the deceased

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person after the funeral, to get together with loved ones on special days, and to gradually return to normal activities. However, if the loss cannot be coped with, seeking professional help is the best step.

4.2. Children in Loss and Grief

Grief is a different phenomenon for each individual in life. For this reason, different grief reactions may be observed depending on the age of the person in the face of loss.

Children's grief reactions sometimes differ. Factors that are generally effective in the formation of reactions are developmental status, personality traits, parents' reactions to grief, the level of relationship between siblings, and the level of perception of grief by the people around them in their social lives. Depending on the child's development and age; who, where, when and how he/she died, the cultural values and religious beliefs of the family and the environment determine how the child will go through this process.

Children are aware of death. They witness the death of living creatures around them, and they talk about death on television, in movies, in the media and in their games. Death is a part of life. For this reason, talking to children will help them deal with any crisis in a healthy way. The important thing here is to provide information appropriate to the child's age, level, and developmental stage.

Plain, short, clear statements and honest explanations make it easier for children to cope with sadness. Children are very good observers. They pick up messages about what is said or not said, when, where and by whom. Interrupting communication, avoiding the topic, increases children's perception of death as unknown, mysterious, hidden and worrying. It is important to give information that the child understands and needs.

In adolescence, the situation is different. During this period, thoughts of death are very common, but the interest in death is combined with a defiance of death. Since adolescents are now capable of abstract thinking, they begin to question whether forms such as spirits or ghosts exist, and if so, what happens when they die or the physical changes that occur. With the development of abstract thinking, adolescents begin to deal with the concept of death in a different way, as thinking about death, worrying about it, and trying to cope with this thought

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requires complex mental activity. Thus, they can better comprehend the situation of death, the process, and its consequences, and can support their families and stand by them.

4.2.1. Giving News of Death to Children

The most important thing for a child experiencing loss is that the parent feels the pain and is there for the child who is suffering. When there is a loss in the family, adults can sometimes have the wrong idea that children are not suffering as much as they are. Parents should first of all help the child express their feelings. Talking about the distress, loneliness and sadness, happy times in the past, plans for the future and general distress is very important for both the child and other family members.

The child should not be told directly about the death of a family member. This may cause the child to go into sudden shock. The event should be explained to the child gradually. The child should be told that he/she could not be saved despite all efforts and his/her emotional state should be shared.

The facts about the loss should be told to children directly, concretized in a way appropriate to their age, level, and developmental stage, avoiding abstract concepts as much as possible, in a simple, clear and understandable way, in an environment where the child feels safe, at a time when the child is ready, by people with whom the child is in close contact. When faced with unexpected questions from the child, it should be stated that time is needed to think. Since children take adults as role models, it is important that adults do not suppress their own grieving processes and share their feelings with the child. Children's inaccurate information and ideas about the loss should be corrected. The place where it is told is important for the child, so a quiet room should be found, the child should be seated and told that something important is going to be talked about. The child should be told who the deceased is and how he/she died and should be prepared for the child's reactions. The child may suddenly start crying, shouting, ask questions, or just sit and try to make sense of it.

When talking to the child, the sentences we choose about the deceased person are important. Expressions such as "he is looking down on us now", "he will sleep forever", "he has gone somewhere else and will never come back" should not be used, and abstract concepts

such as the soul should not be included in our narrative. This can create the impression that everyone who travels or sleeps dies.

Sometimes children may blame themselves for the death of the deceased person and hold themselves responsible for their death. In this case, they should be talked to, and the real cause of the death should be explained. Children come out of guilt in an environment where they are accepted, safe, loved and their feelings are understood.

4.2.2. Attending the Funeral

Since children in the Early Childhood Education Period (3-6 years of age) have not yet formed a certain perception of death, funeral ceremonies do not make sense or create a situation that increases the existing confusion. It is not appropriate to take children under the age of six to funeral ceremonies unless there is a special circumstance, as parents may not be able to pay enough attention to their children during this period of intense grief and mourning.

The child's participation in the funeral is a situation that should be decided according to the child's age, level, and developmental stage, taking into account individual characteristics. Removing children from their own home or the cemetery during the funeral ceremony and directing them to exaggerated games or entertainment by adults at that time may cause the child to develop a sense of guilt about the death of his/her parent and cause the grief to become complicated.

Trying to force a child who clearly expresses that he/she does not want to attend the funeral, using coercive sentences such as "this is our last duty", "we have to be there", etc. constitutes a threat to his/her mental health. The most important thing that can be done in this situation is to give the child information about what will happen there, to explain that there is nothing to be afraid of and to encourage the child to think about it again. In conclusion, it should be made clear that if the child agrees to come, it is appreciated, but if the child refuses to come despite all explanations, it should be understood.

5. Cognitive Grief Therapy with Families

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Death and grief is a negative situation that affects the whole family. The loss of a family member leads to the loss of hopes, dreams, expectations, and the family system. This situation causes a change in the balance within the family, as loss and grief is a family problem.

The grieving process is actually a situation that does not require intervention and is part of people's lives. However, sometimes the process does not go as expected. In cases such as traumatic grief, which is observed in the grieving individual instead of unusual and healthy grief according to social criteria, the individual or family should be helped.

It is important to receive support from professionals and relatives during the grieving process. It is valuable to have family members, relatives, friends, neighbors, and other sources of professional support such as therapists, counselors, nurses, social workers, physicians, and support groups on the side of family members during the grieving process.

Professional support in the grieving process can be divided into two categories: grief counseling and grief therapy. Grief counseling is a method carried out to help survivors adapt to life after the loss of a loved one. Its aim is to help individuals cope with the pain they have experienced as a result of loss, to help them get their lives back on track, to clarify the reality of the loss and to ensure that the individual maintains a connection with the person they have lost while continuing their life. Grief therapy, on the other hand, is a support provided by experts in the field to ensure the identification and resolution of the conflict related to separation in individuals with chronic, delayed, exaggerated or physical symptoms.

5.1. Cognitive Family Therapy After Loss

Cognitive Family Therapy was created by Aeron Beck and his colleagues. According to the cognitive view, depression stems from the schemas that a person creates starting from the early stages of his/her life. According to the cognitive model, the person first has negative schemas about himself/herself, and then begins to perceive the whole world negatively. This feeling of negativity becomes an inhibiting thought for him/her. This problem in cognitive aspects leads to the formation of depressive personality.

Individuals with a cognitive disorder go through life with extremely negative emotions. They perceive their lives as extremely negatively charged, full of insurmountable obstacles,

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unenjoyable, distressing, and unsatisfying. They have no idea when their current problems will end.

The goal of cognitive therapy is to change unrealistic beliefs, thoughts, feelings, and self-perception. The aim of cognitive-behavioral therapy is primarily to reveal the thoughts that are unrealistic or problematic for the individual. When the problematic thought is expressed, the effect of that thought on the individual is also resolved. First of all, the connection between these thoughts and the difficult situation is important.

The attitudes and behaviors of one family member trigger the feelings, thoughts, and behaviors of other family members. In this process, instability increases in family members, which leads the family into unhappy, restless, and conflicted relationships.

Cognitive family therapy focuses on the factors that reveal and maintain all kinds of influences on the individual's behavior. In this therapy method, positive reinforcement, warnings, punishments, and rewards are important for the emergence and maintenance of behavior. If behavioral change is to be achieved, the most important factors are to identify the factors that create behaviors and to know how to benefit from positive reinforcements.

Cognitive family therapy usually consists of three phases. In the initial phase, the patient's existing problem is revealed. In order to prepare for the active phases of therapy, patients and their families are informed about the process through psychoeducation. Then the treatment process begins. After the clinical assessment and psychoeducation are completed, the more active middle phase begins. In this phase, cognitive behavioral techniques, and interventions appropriate to the main findings of the patient are applied. As soon as the symptoms decrease, the last phase is started. In this phase, the intensity of the treatment is reduced and finalized according to the situation.

5.2. Family Grief Therapy Interventions

In short, Family Grief Therapies are therapy methods aimed at eliminating communication problems between family members or strengthening communication between them. Although family members may experience many conflicts within the relationship that require therapy, the most common problems are as follows: Personal problems that become

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persistent between spouses and cannot be overcome, problems that cause dependency between family members, momentary, periodic or situational depressions, children's adolescence problems, age-based problems, psychiatric and physiological disorders, children's behavioral problems, lack of consensus in decision-making processes, domestic violence, loss and grieving periods.

Preventive and supportive interventions within the scope of professional support for families in the grieving process are important. These practices enable the family to cope with the feelings and thoughts brought about by loss and grief, learn to live with grief and adapt to life.

When assessing grieving families; the identity of the deceased person, his/her role and contribution to the family system, the manner of death, the impact of this death on family members and funeral rituals should be listened to first. Then, the family's history of coping with grief and relationship should be obtained. The basic structure, ways of coping with difficult events, patterns passed down through generations, strengths and weaknesses of the family should be determined.

Grief support groups, which are among the sources of professional support in grief, have been found to be an effective and appropriate way to heal in the grieving process, as these groups provide opportunities for participants to work with grief, reconcile with their losses and find meaning in life, and enable participants to obtain useful information. Support groups led by an expert provide participants with an opportunity to:

- a. Come together with individuals who have similar experiences, feelings, and thoughts,
- b. Be able to analyze the feeling of isolation in the grieving process,
- c. Receive emotional, physical and spiritual support in a safe and non-critical environment
- d. Reveal their feelings and thoughts about grief,
- e. Provide support and guidance not only for oneself but also for others
- f. Learn new ways of solving problems,
- g. Change all negative thoughts about the world into positive thoughts for individuals who feel the world is unsafe,
- h. Explore the meaning of life and death,
- i. Be in a supportive environment that fosters the joy of life, reconnection and hope.

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6. Conclusion

Losing a loved one with whom one was close to, with whom one has shared experiences, is undoubtedly a very painful process. As each person has his/her own individual differences, the age of the person lost, the reason for the loss, the relationship with the individual, and the role of the individual in the family affect the level and duration of the grieving process. Grieving individuals experience significant changes. The diversity of factors affecting these changes causes the individual to go through the grieving process in a healthy, pathological, or traumatic way. Grief counseling should be used to help survivors adapt to life after the loss of a loved one, or grief therapy should be used to identify and resolve the conflict related to separation after loss. The family is a whole in the process of loss and grief. In order to ensure this integrity, individuals need to act in consensus in decision-making and implementation. Preventive and supportive interventions within the scope of professional support to families in the grieving process are important. These practices enable families to cope with the feelings and thoughts brought about by loss and subsequent grief, learn to live with grief and adapt to life.

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